

- Ahland, Colleen. 2010. 'Noun Incorporation and Predicate Classifiers in Gumuz'. *Journal of African Languages and Linguistics* 31:159–203.
- . 2012. 'A Grammar of Northern and Southern Gumuz'. Doctoral dissertation, Eugene: University of Oregon.
- Amiridze, Nino. 2006. *Reflexivization Strategies in Georgian*. Utrecht: Lot.
- Aoki, Haruo. 1965. 'Nez Perce Grammar'. Doctoral dissertation, Berkeley (CA): University of California.
- Arensen, Jon. 1982. *Murle Grammar*. Juba: Summer Institute of Linguistics.
- Arkadiev, Peter, and Yury Lander. 2020. 'The Northwest Caucasian Languages'. In *The Oxford Handbook of Languages of the Caucasus*, edited by Maria Polinsky, 369–446. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Aronson, Howard I. 1990. *Georgian: A Reading Grammar*. Ohio (OH): Slavica Publishers.
- Auderset, Sandra. 2021. 'The Antipassive and Its Relationship to Person Markers'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 385–425. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Austin, Peter. 2013. *A Grammar of Diyari, South Australia*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bahrt, Nicklas. 2021. *Voice Syncretism*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Baker, Mark, and Jonathan Bobaljik. 2017. 'On Inherent and Dependent Theories of Ergative Case'. In *The Oxford Handbook of Ergativity*, edited by Jessica Coon, Diane Massam, and Lisa deMena Travis, 111–34. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Baker, Mark C., Roberto Aranovich, and Lucía A. Golluscio. 2005. 'Two Types of Syntactic Noun Incorporation: Noun Incorporation in Mapudungun and Its Typological Implications'. *Language* 81 (1): 138–76.
- Bickel, Balthasar. 1996. *Aspect, Mood, and Time in Belhare: Studies in the Semantics-Pragmatics Interface of a Himalayan Language*. Zürich: ASAS.
- . 2004. 'Hidden Syntax in Belhare'. In *Himalayan Languages: Past and Present*, edited by Anju Saxena, De Gruyter Mouton, 141–90. Berlin.
- . 2010. 'Capturing Particulars and Universals in Clause Linkage: A Multivariate Analysis'. In *Clause-Hierarchy and Clause-Linking: The Syntax and Pragmatics Interface*, edited by Isabelle Bril, 51–101. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 2011. 'Multivariate Typology and Field Linguistics: A Case Study on Detransitivization in Kiranti (Sino-Tibetan)'. In *Proceedings of Conference on Language Documentation and Linguistic Theory 3*, edited by Peter Austin K., Oliver Bond, David Nathan, and Lutz Marten, 3:3–13. London: SOAS.
- . 2017. 'Belhare'. In *The Sino-Tibetan Languages*, edited by Graham Thurgood and Randy J. LaPolla, 2nd ed., 696–721. London: Routledge.
- Bickel, Balthasar, and Martin Gaenszle. 2015. 'First Person Objects, Antipassives, and the Political History of the Southern Kirant'. *Journal of South Asian Languages and Linguistics* 2 (1): 63–86.
- Bickel, Balthasar, Martin Gaenszle, Arjun Rai, Prem Dhoj Rai, Shree Kumar Rai, and Vishnu S Rai. 2007. 'Two Ways of Suspending Object Agreement in Puma: Between Incorporation, Antipassivization, and Optional Agreement'. *Himalayan Linguistics* 7:1–19.
- Birnbaum, Salomo A. 1979. *Yiddish: A Survey and a Grammar*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.

- Bittner, Maria. 1987. 'On the Semantics of the Greenlandic Antipassive and Related Constructions'. *International Journal of American Linguistics* 53 (2): 1–60.
- Boeder, Winfried. 1979. 'Ergative Syntax and Morphology in Language Change: The South Caucasian Languages'. In *Ergativity: Towards a Theory of Grammatical Relations*, edited by Frans Plank, 435–80. London: Academic Press.
- Bok-Bennema, Reineke. 1991. *Case and Agreement in Inuit*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Bugaeva, Anna. 2015. 'Valency Classes in Ainu'. In *Valency Classes in the World's Languages*, edited by Andrej L. Malchukov and Bernard Comrie, 807–54. *Comparative Handbooks of Linguistics*, 1.1-1.2. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- . 2021. 'Unspecified Participant: A Case of Antipassive in Ainu'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 213–46. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Bugaeva, Anna, and Miki Kobayashi. 2022. 'Verbal Valency'. In *Handbook of the Ainu Language*, edited by Anna Bugaeva, 515–48. Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Campbell, Dennis R. M. 2007. 'Mood and Modality in Hurrian'. Doctoral dissertation, Chicago (IL): University of Chicago.
- . 2015. *Mood and Modality in Hurrian*. Winona Lake (IN): Eisenbrauns.
- Campbell, Lyle, Luis Díaz, and Fernando Ángel. 2020. *Nivaclé Grammar*. Salt Lake City: University of Utah Press.
- Charney, Jean O. 1989. 'A Grammatical Sketch of the Comanche Language'. Doctoral dissertation, Boulder (CO): University of Colorado.
- . 1993. *A Grammar of Comanche*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.
- Chirikba, Viacheslav A. 2003. *Abkhaz*. München. Lincom Europa.
- Chung, Sandra. 2020. *Chamorro Grammar*. Santa Cruz: University of California.
- Chung, Sandra, and William A. Ladusaw. 2001. 'Restriction and Saturation'. University of California, Santa Cruz.
- Clendon, Mark. 2014. *Worrorra: A Language of the North-West Kimberley Coast*. Adelaide: University of Adelaide.
- Comrie, Bernard, Diana Forker, and Zaira Khalilova. 2016. 'Antipassives in Nakh-Daghestanian Languages'. Abstract presented at the Workshop 'Correlations of valency-changing operations within and across languages' within '46th Poznań Linguistic Meeting', Poznań, September 15.
- Comrie, Bernard, Diana Forker, Zaira Khalilova, and Helma Van den Berg. 2021. 'Antipassives in Nakh-Daghestanian Languages: Exploring the Margins of a Construction'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 515–48. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Comrie, Bernard, Madzhid Khalilov, and Zaira Khalilova. 2015. 'Valency and Valency Classes in Bezhta'. In *Valency Classes in the World's Languages*, edited by Andrej L. Malchukov and Bernard Comrie, 1:541–70. *Comparative Handbooks of Linguistics*, 1.1-1.2. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Comrie, Bernard, and Zaira Khalilova. 2015. 'The Antipassive Alternation in Bezhta'. Presentation, MPI-EVA, Leipzig.
- Cooreman, Ann. 1983. 'Topic Continuity and the Voicing System of an Ergative Language: Chamorro'. In *Topic Continuity in Discourse: A Quantitative Cross-Language Study*, edited by Talmy Givón, 425–89. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 1987. *Transitivity and Discourse Continuity in Chamorro Narratives*. Berlin: De

- Gruyter Mouton.
- . 1988. ‘The Antipassive in Chamorro: Variations on the Theme of Transitivity’. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 561–93. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 1994. ‘A Functional Typology of Antipassives’. In *Voice: Form and Function*, edited by Barbara A. Fox and Paul J. Hopper, 49–88. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Creissels, Denis. 2021. ‘Antipassive Derivation in Soninke (West Mande)’. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 293–314. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 2024. *Transitivity, Valency, and Voice*. Oxford (UK): Oxford University Press.
- Creissels, Denis, and Djibril Dramé. 2018. ‘Transitivity and Incorporation in Soninke’. In *Transitivity in African Languages*, edited by Rose-Juliet Anyanwu, 37–54. Cologne: Rüdiger Köppe.
- Crook, Harold D. 1999. ‘The Phonology and Morphology of Nez Perce Stress’. Doctoral dissertation, Los Angeles: University of California.
- De Jong Boudreault, Lynda. 2009. ‘A Grammar of Sierra Popoluca (Soteapanec, a Mixe-Zoquean Language)’. Doctoral dissertation, Austin: University of Texas.
- Deal, Amy R. 2010a. ‘Ergative Case and the Transitive Subject: A View from Nez Perce’. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 28 (1): 73–120.
- . 2010b. ‘Topics in the Nez Perce Verbs’. Doctoral dissertation, Amherst: University of Massachusetts.
- Dimmendaal, Gerrit J. 2009. ‘Tima’. In *Coding Participant Marking: Construction Types in Twelve African Languages*, edited by Gerrit J. Dimmendaal, 331–53. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Dixon, R. M. W. 2002. *Australian Languages: Their Nature and Development*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Dunn, Michael J. 1999. ‘A Grammar of Chukchi’. Doctoral dissertation, Canberra: Australian National University.
- Edygarova, Svetlana. 2022. ‘Udmurt’. In *The Oxford Guide to the Uralic Languages*, edited by Marianne Bakró-Nagy, Johanna Laakso, and Elena Skribnik, 507–22. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- England, Nora C. 1983. *A Grammar of Mam, a Mayan Language*. Austin: University of Texas Press.
- . 1988. ‘Mam Voice’. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 525–45. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 2017. ‘Mam’. In *The Mayan Languages*, edited by Judith Aissen, Nora C. England, and Roberto Zavala, 500–569. London: Routledge.
- Evans, Nicholas. 1999. ‘Why Argument Affixes in Polysynthetic Languages Are Not Pronouns: Evidence from Bininj Gun-Wok’. *Sprachtypologie und Universalienforschung* 52 (3/4): 255–81.
- . 2002. ‘The True Status of Grammatical Object Affixes: Evidence from Bininj Gun-Wok’. In *Problems of Polysynthesis*, edited by Nicholas Evans and Hans-Jürgen Sasse, 15–50. Berlin: Akademie Verlag.
- . 2003. *Bininj Gun-Wok: A Pan-Dialectal Grammar of Mayali, Kunwinjku and Kune*. Canberra: Pacific Linguistics, Research School of Pacific and Asian Studies.
- . 2017. ‘Polysynthesis in Northern Australia’. In *The Oxford Handbook of Polysynthesis*, edited by Michael Fortescue, Marianne Mithun, and Nicholas Evans, 1–27. Oxford:

- Oxford University Press.
- Evans, Nicholas, Alice Gaby, and Rachel Nordlinger. 2007. 'Valency Mismatches and the Coding of Reciprocity in Australian Languages'. *Linguistic Typology* 11 (3): 541–97.
- Fabre, Alain. 2017. 'Morphosyntax of the Nivacle Verb and Some Comparisons with Other Languages of the Gran Chaco Region and Elsewhere'.
- Forker, Diana. 2017. 'Ergativity in Nakh-Daghestanian'. In *The Oxford Handbook of Ergativity*, edited by Jessica Coon, Diane Massam, and Lisa deMena Travis, 851–72. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Fortescue, Michael D. 1984. *West Greenlandic*. London: Croom Helm.
- Friesen, Dianne, Mana D. Isaac, Ali Gaston, and Mana Samuel. 2017. *A Grammar of Moloko*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Friesen, Dianne, and Megan Mamalis. 2008. 'The Moloko Verb Phrase'. *SIL Electronic Working Papers*.
- Geniušienė, Emma. 1987. *The Typology of Reflexives*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Georg, Stefan. 2007. *A Descriptive Grammar of Ket (Yenisei-Ostyak): PART I: Introduction, Phonology and Morphology*. Folkestone (UK): Global Oriental.
- Gerds, Donna B., and Mercedes Hinkson. 1996. 'Salish Lexical Suffixes: A Case of Decategorialization'. In *Proceedings of the Conference on Conceptual Structure, Discourse, and Language*, edited by Adele Goldberg, 163–76. Stanford (CA): CSLI.
- Gerds, Donna B., and Thomas E. Hukari. 2006. 'The Halkomelem Middle: A Complex Network of Constructions'. *Anthropological Linguistics* 48 (1): 44–81.
- Gerds, Donna. 2010. 'Ditransitive Constructions in Halkomelem Salish: A Direct Object/Oblique Object Language'. In *Studies in Ditransitive Constructions: A Comparative Handbook*, edited by Andrej L. Malchukov, Martin Haspelmath, and Bernard Comrie, 563–610. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Gerds, Donna B. 1988. *Object and Absolutive in Halkomelem Salish*. London: Routledge.
- . 2001. 'Incorporation'. In *The Handbook of Morphology*, edited by Andrew Spencer and Arnold M. Zwicky, 84–100. Oxford (UK): Blackwell.
- . 2003. 'The Morphosyntax of Halkomelem Lexical Suffixes'. *International Journal of American Linguistics* 69 (4): 345–56.
- Gerds, Donna B., and Thomas E. Hukari. 2000. 'Multiple Antipassives in Halkomelem Salish'. *Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society* 26 (2): 51–62.
- Grondona, Verónica M. 1998. 'A Grammar of Mocoví'. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh.
- Guillaume, Antoine. 2008. *A Grammar of Cavineña*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- . 2013. 'Reduplication'.
- . 2014. 'The Interaction of Reduplication with Word Classes and Transitivity in Cavineña'. In *Reduplication in Indigenous Languages of South America*, edited by Gale G. Gomez and Hein van der Voort, 313–42. Leiden: Brill.
- Hamann, Jakob, Sebastian Banks, Doreen Georgi, and Jochen Trommer. 2010. 'On the Syntax and Morphology of Double Agreement in Lavukaleve'. In *2 in Agreement*, 197–225. Leipzig: University of Leipzig.
- Harris, Alice C. 1981. *Georgian Syntax: A Study in Relational Grammar*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge.
- Heath, Jeffrey. 2014. 'Grammar of Humburi Senni (Songhay of Hombori, Mali)'. Unpublished manuscript.
- Heaton, Raina. 2017. 'A Typology of Antipassives, with Speciation Reference to Mayan'.

- Doctoral dissertation, Manoa: University of Hawaii.
- . 2021. ‘Antipassive and Antipassive-Type Constructions in Mayan Languages’. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 549–78. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Hewitt, George. 1995. *Georgian: A Structural Reference Grammar*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Hewitt, George B. 1979. *Abkhaz*. Amsterdam: North-Holland.
- Holvoet, Axel. 2017. ‘Antipassive Reflexives in Latvian’. *Baltic Linguistics* 8:57–96.
- . 2019. ‘On the Heterogeneity of Deaccusative Reflexives’. *STUF-Language Typology and Universals* 72 (3): 401–19.
- Holvoet, Axel, and Anna Daugavet. 2020. ‘Antipassive Reflexive Constructions in Latvian: A Corpus-Based Analysis’. *Baltic Linguistics* 11:241–90.
- Holvoet, Axel, Marta Grzybowska, and Agnieszka Rembiałkowska. 2015. ‘Middle Voice Reflexives and Argument Structure in Baltic’. In *Voice and Argument Structure in Baltic*, edited by Axel Holvoet and Nicole Nau, 181–209. 2. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Hualde, José I., and Jon Ortiz de Urbina. 2003. *A Grammar of Basque*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Huber, Juliette. 2011. ‘A Grammar of Makalero: A Papuan Language of East Timor’. Utrecht: LOT.
- Jacobs, Neil G., Ellen F. Prince, and Johan van der Auwera. 1994. ‘Yiddish’. In *The Germanic Languages*, edited by Ekkehard König and Johan van der Auwera, 388–419. London: Routledge.
- Jacobsen Jr, William H. 1964. ‘A Grammar of the Washo Language’. Doctoral dissertation, Berkeley: University of California.
- Jacobsen Jr., William H. 1979. ‘Why Does Washo Lack a Passive?’ In *Ergativity: Towards a Theory of Grammatical Relations*, edited by Frans Plank, 145–60. London: Academic Press.
- Jacques, Guillaume. 2012a. ‘Argument Demotion in Japhug Rgyalrong’. In *Ergativity, Valency and Voice*, edited by Gilles Authier and Katharina Haude, 199–225. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- . 2012b. ‘From Denominal Derivation to Incorporation’. *Lingua* 122 (11): 1207–31.
- . 2019. ‘Verbal Valency and Japhug / Tibetan Language Contact’. *Journal of Language Contact* 12 (1): 116–40.
- . 2021a. *A Grammar of Japhug*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- . 2021b. ‘Antipassive Derivations in Sino-Tibetan/Trans-Himalayan and Their Sources’. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 427–79. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Juárez, Cristian, and Albert Álvarez González. 2017. ‘The Antipassive Marking in Mocoví: Forms and Functions’. In *Verb Valency Changes: Theoretical and Typological Perspectives*, edited by Albert Álvarez González and Ia Navarro, 228–55. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 2021. ‘Explaining the Antipassive-Causative Syncretism in Mocoví (Guaycuruan)’. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 315–47. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Juárez, Cristian R. 2013. ‘Sistemas de Alineación En El Mocoví (Guayucurú, Argentina) Hablado En Colonia Aborigen’. M.A. Dissertation, Sonora: University of Sonora.

- . 2023. ‘A Typology of Valence-Changing Mechanisms and Related Verb Modifications in Northern Chaco Mocoquí (Guaycuruan, Argentina)’. Doctoral dissertation, Austin (TX): University of Texas.
- Kahn, Lily. 2016. ‘Yiddish’. In *Handbook of Jewish Languages*, edited by Lily Kahn and Aaron D. Rubin, 639–747. Leiden: Brill.
- Kalnača, Andra, and Ilze Lokmane. 2021. **Latvian Grammar*. Riga: University of Latvia Press.
- Kozinsky, Isaac, Vladimir P. Nedjalkov, and Maria S. Polinskaja. 1988. ‘Antipassive in Chukchee: Oblique Object, Object Incorporation, Zero Object’. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 651–706. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Kurebito, Tokusu. 2008. ‘Valency-Changing in Chukchi’. In *Linguistic Typology of the North*, 73–86. Tokyo: Research Institute for Languages and Cultures of Asia and Africa (ILCAA), Tokyo University of Foreign Studies.
- . 2012. ‘An Outline of Valency-Reducing Operations in Chukchi’. In *Objectivization and Subjectivization: A Typology of Voice Systems*, edited by Wataru Nakamura, Ritsuko Kikusawa, and Kokuritsu Minzokugaku Hakubutsukan, 177–89. Osaka: National Museum of Ethnology.
- Lock, Arnold H. 2011. *Abau Grammar*. Ukarumpa, Papua New Guinea: SIL-PNG Academic Publications.
- Loughnane, Robyn. 2009. ‘A Grammar of Oksapmin’. Doctoral dissertation, Melbourne: University of Melbourne.
- Luchina, Elena. 2023. ‘Reflexive Constructions in Yiddish’. In *Reflexive Constructions in the World’s Languages*, edited by Katarzyna Janic, Nicoletta Puddu, and Martin Haspelmath, 365–83. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Maksunova, Zoya V. 2004. ‘Incorporation and Word Formation in Ket’. In *Languages and Prehistory of Central Siberia*, edited by Edward J. Vajda, 143–50. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Margolis, Rebecca. 2011. *Basic Yiddish: A Grammar and Workbook*. London: Routledge.
- Maslova, Elena. 2003. *A Grammar of Kolyma Yukaghir*. De Gruyter Mouton.
- . 2007. ‘Reciprocals in Yukaghir Languages’. In *Reciprocal Constructions*, edited by Vladimir P. Nedjalkov, 1835–63. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Massam, Diane. 2001. ‘Pseudo Noun Incorporation in Niuean’. *Natural Language and Linguistic Theory* 19 (1): 153–97.
- . 2020. *Niuean: Predicates and Arguments in an Isolating Language*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- McGregor, William. 1990. *A Functional Grammar of Gooniyandi*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 1992. ‘The Semantic of Ergative Marking in Gooniyandi’. *Linguistics* 30 (2): 275–318.
- Mithun, Marianne. 1984. ‘The Evolution of Noun Incorporation’. *Language* 60 (4): 847–94.
- . 2000. ‘Valency-Changing Derivation in Central Alaskan Yupik’. In *Changing Valency: Case Study in Transitivity*, edited by R.M.W. Dixon and Alexandra Y. Aikhenvald, 84–114. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Miyaoka, Osahito. 2012. *A Grammar of Central Alaskan Yupik (CAY)*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- . 2015. ‘Valency Classes in Central Alaskan Yupik, an Eskimoan Language’. In *Valency Classes in the World’s Languages*, edited by Andrej L. Malchukov and Bernard Comrie, 2:1165–1204. Comparative Handbooks of Linguistics, 1.1-1.2. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.

- Morin, Yves-Charles, and Etienne Tiffou. 1988. 'Passives in Burushaski'. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 493–524. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Mubarak, Suzan A. 2009. 'Tima Word Structure (Noun and Verb)'. M.A. Dissertation, Khartoum: University of Khartoum.
- Munshi, Sadaf. 2006. 'Jammu and Kashmir Burushaski: Language, Language Contact, and Change'. Doctoral dissertation, Austin (TX): University of Texas.
- Nedjalkov, Igor V., and Vladimir P. Nedjalkov. 2007. 'Reciprocals, Sociatives, Comitatives, and Assistives in Yakut'. In *Reciprocal Constructions*, edited by Vladimir P. Nedjalkov, 1095–1161. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Nedjalkov, Vladimir P. 2006. 'Reciprocal Constructions of Turkic Languages in the Typological Perspective'. *Turkic Languages* 10 (1): 3–46.
- Nefedov, Andrey, Andrey L. Malchukov, and Edward Vajda. 2010. 'Ditransitive Constructions in Ket'. In *Studies in Ditransitive Constructions: A Comparative Handbook*, edited by Andrej Malchukov, Martin Haspelmath, and Bernard Comrie, 352–81. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- O'Herin, Peter. 2020. 'Abaza and Abkhaz'. In *The Oxford Handbook of Languages of the Caucasus*, edited by Maria Polinsky, 447–88. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Olthof, Marieke, Eva van Lier, Tjeu Claessen, Swintha Danielsen, Katharina Haude, Nico Lehmann, Maarten Mous, Elisabeth Verhoeven, Eline Visser, and Marine Vuillermet. 2020. 'Verb-Based Restrictions on Noun Incorporation across Languages'. *Linguistic Typology* 25 (2): 211–56.
- Patz, Elisabeth. 2002. *A Grammar of the Kuku Yalanji Language of North Queensland*. Canberra: Research School of Pacific and Asian Studies The Australian National University.
- Payne, Doris, Mitsuyo Hamaya, and Peter Jacobs. 1994. 'Active, Inverse and Passive in Maasai'. In *Voice and Inversion*, edited by Talmy Givón, 283–315. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Payne, Doris L. 2015. 'Perspectives on Nilotic Verb Composition: Why Can't We Agree on the Maa Verb?' In *Nilo-Saharan – Models and Descriptions*, edited by Angelika Mietzner and Anne Storch, 211–29. Nilo-Saharan 28. Köln: Rüdiger Köppe Verlag.
- . 2021. 'The Profile and Development of the Maa (Eastern Nilotic) Antipassive'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 447–381. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Payne, Thomas E. 1995. 'Object Incorporation in Panare'. *International Journal of American Linguistics* 61 (3): 295–311.
- Payne, Thomas E., and Doris L. Payne. 2013. *A Typological Grammar of Panare: A Caribbean Language of Venezuela*. Leiden: Brill.
- Polinsky, Maria. 2017. 'Antipassive'. In *The Oxford Handbook of Ergativity*, edited by Jessica Coon, Diane Massam, and Lisa deMena Travis, 208–331. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Price, Samantha. 2018. 'An Analysis of the Syntax of Comanche'. Northeastern University.
- Ribeiro, Eduardo R. 2001. 'Valence, Voice, and Noun Incorporation in Karajá'. *Proceedings of the Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society* 27:229–43.
- . 2012. 'A Grammar of Karajá'. Doctoral dissertation, Chicago (IL): University of Chicago.
- Rose, Françoise. 2023a. 'Reflexive Constructions and Middle Marking in Mojeño Trinitario'. In *Reflexive Constructions in the World's Languages*, edited by Katarzyna Janic, Nicoletta

- Puddu, and Martin Haspelmath, 769–95. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- . 2023b. ‘Valency Changes’. Lyon.
- Rude, Noël. 1982. ‘Promotion and Topicality of Nez Perce Objects’. *Proceedings of the Eighth Annual Meeting of the Berkeley Linguistics Society*, 463–83.
- Rude, Noël. 1985. ‘Studies in Nez Perce Grammar and Discourse’. Doctoral dissertation, Eugene: University of Oregon.
- . 1986. ‘Transitivity and the Direct Object in Nez Perce’. *International Journal of American Linguistics* 52 (2): 124–53.
- . 1988. ‘Ergative, Passive, and Antipassive in Nez Perce: A Discourse Perspective’. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 547–60. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Sadock, Jerrold. 1980. ‘Noun Incorporation in Greenlandic: A Case of Syntactic Word Formation’. *Language* 56 (2): 300–319.
- Sadock, Jerrold M. 2003. *A Grammar of Kalaallisut (West Greenlandic Inuttut)*. München: Lincom Europa.
- Sapién, Racquel-Maria, Natalia Cáceres Arandía, Spike Gildea, and Sérgio Meira. 2021. ‘Antipassive in the Cariban Family’. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Satō, Tomomi. 2016. ‘A Classification of the Types of Noun Incorporation in Ainu and Its Implications for Morphosyntactic Typology’. *Studia Orientalia Electronica* 117:83–93.
- . 2022. ‘Noun Incorporation in Ainu’. In *Handbook of the Ainu Language*, edited by Anna Bugaeva, 549–71. Boston: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Schmidt, Bodil K. 2003. ‘West Greenlandic Antipassive’. *Nordlyd (Proceedings of the 19th Scandinavian Conference of Linguistics)* 31 (2): 385–99.
- Seiter, William J. 1980. ‘Studies in Niuean Syntax’. Doctoral dissertation, University of California: San Diego.
- Sharpe, Margaret C. 1972. *Alawa Phonology and Grammar*. Canberra: Australian Institute of Aboriginal Studies.
- Smeets, Ineke. 2008. *A Grammar of Mapuche*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Stirtz, Timothy M. 2012. *A Grammar of Gaahmg: A Nilo-Saharan Language of Sudan*. Utrecht: LOT.
- . 2014. ‘Ergative, Antipassive and Other Verb Derivational Morphemes in Gaahmg’. *Journal of African Languages and Linguistics* 35 (2): 243–72.
- Terril, Angela. 2004. ‘Coordination in Lavukaleve’. In *Coordinating Constructions*, edited by Martin Haspelmath, 427–43. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Terrill, Angela. 2003. *A Grammar of Lavukaleve*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- . 2011. ‘Languages in Contact: An Exploration of Stability and Change in the Solomon Islands’. *Oceanic Linguistics* 50 (2): 312–37.
- Topping, Donald M., and Bernadita C. Dungca. 1973. *Chamorro Reference Grammar*. Honolulu: University Press of Hawaii.
- Tsunoda, Tasaku. 1988. ‘Antipassive in Warrungu and Other Australian Languages’. In *Passive and Voice*, edited by Masayoshi Shibatani, 595–649. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 2006. ‘Reflexive and Middle Constructions of Warrungu (Australia)’. In *Voice and Grammatical Relations: In Honor of Masayoshi Shibatani*, edited by Tasaku Tsunoda and Tarō Kageyama, 299–333. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 2011. *A Grammar of Warrongo*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.

- Tuite, Kevin. 2003. 'Liminal Morphosyntax: Georgian Deponents and Their Kin'. *Chicago Linguistic Society* 39 (1): 774–93.
- Vaida, Edward J. 2004. *Ket*. München: Lincom Europa.
- Vajda, Edward J. 2003. 'Ket Verb Structure in Typological Perspective'. *STUF-Language Typology and Universals* 56 (1–2): 55–92.
- , ed. 2004. *Languages and Prehistory of Central Siberia*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- . 2015. 'Valency Properties of the Ket Verb Clause'. In *Valency Classes in the World's Languages*, edited by Andrej L. Malchukov and Bernard Comrie, 629–68. Comparative Handbooks of Linguistics, 1.1-1.2. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Vidal, Alejandra, and Doris L. Payne. 2021. 'Polyfunctional Vanka- in Nivačle and the Antipassive Category'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 349–81. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Vigus, Meagan. 2018. 'Antipassive Constructions: Correlations of Form and Function across Languages'. *Linguistic Typology* 22 (3): 339–84.
- Vinokurova, Nadezhda. 2005. *Lexical Categories and Argument Structure: A Study with Reference to Sakha*. Utrecht: LOT.
- Visser, Eline. 2022. *A Grammar of Kalamang*. Berlin: Language Science Press.
- Visser, Eline, Eva van Lier, and Marieke Olthof. 2019. 'The Semantics and Frequency of Incorporating Verbs in Kalamang'. Abstract.
- Wegener, Claudia. 2012. *A Grammar of Savosavo*. Berlin: De Gruyter Mouton.
- Westerlund, Torbjörn. 2015. *A Grammatical Sketch of Ngarla (Ngayarta, Pama-Nyungan)*. Canberra: Asia-Pacific Linguistics College of Asia and the Pacific The Australian National University.
- . 2017. 'Verb Classification in Ngarla (Ngayarta, Pama-Nyungan)'. *Australian Journal of Linguistics* 37 (3): 328–55.
- Whittaker, Graeme. 1982. *The Niuean Language : An Elementary Grammar and Basic Vocabulary*. Alofi, Niue: University of the South Pacific, Niue Centre.
- Winkler, Eberhard. 2001. *Udmurt*. München: Lincom.
- Woodbury, Anthony C. 1981. 'Study of the Chevak Dialect of Central Yup'ik Eskimo'. Doctoral dissertation, Berkeley (CA): University of California.
- Yoshioka, Noboru. 2012. 'A Reference Grammar of Eastern Burushaski'. Doctoral dissertation, Tokyo: Tokyo University of Foreign Studies.
- Zewde, Aster. 1991. 'Gumuz Verb Morphology'. M.A. Dissertation, Addis Ababa: Addis Ababa University.
- Zúñiga, Fernando. 2000. *Mapudungun*. München: Lincom Europa.
- . 2015. 'Valency Classes in Mapudungun'. In *Valency Classes in the World's Languages*, edited by Andrej L. Malchukov and Bernard Comrie, 2:1515–43. Comparative Handbooks of Linguistics, 1.1-1.2. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Zúñiga, Fernando, and Beatriz Fernández. 2021. 'Antipassivization in Basque Revisited'. In *Antipassive: Typology, Diachrony, and Related Constructions*, edited by Katarzyna Janic and Alena Witzlack-Makarevich, 621–40. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Zúñiga, Fernando, and Seppo Kittilä. 2019. *Grammatical Voice*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.